

PLANETARY Health Cluster

FORMED BY

Cluster Brochure

D4.4

Projects GoGreen Next, Planet4Health, Mosaic, Springs, and Tulip have received funding from the European Union's Horizon Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement no. 101137209, 101136652, 101137398, 101137255, and 101136659 respectively. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union and neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Deliverable Overview	
Deliverable No.	D4.4
Work Package	WG3
Dissemination Level	PU
Author(s)	Ivana Ilić, Cátia Sousa (PLANET4HEALTH)
Co-author(s)	WG3 members
Date	13 February 2025
File Name	Cluster Brochure
Status	Final - Submitted
Revision	V1
Reviewed by (if applicable)	

Contents

1. Executive summary	4
2. Introduction	4
2.1. Purpose and scope	4
2.2. Audience	5
3. The brochure	5
3.1. Language and tone	5
3.2. Structure	5
3.3. Design	9
4. Dissemination plan	10
4.1. Target audience	10
4.2. Distribution channels	10
4.3. Monitoring	11
4.4. Timeline	13
5. Conclusion	13
6. Annex 1: Planetary Health Cluster brochure	14

Figures

Figure 1 Folding system of the Planetary Health Brochure	5
Figure 2 Front and back covers of the brochure	6
Figure 3 Interior of the brochure	7
Figure 4 Planetary Health Cluster poster, part of the brochure	8
Figure 5 Two-side view, Planetary Health Cluster brochure and poster	9
Figure 6 Print screen of the monitoring table for the dissemination of the digital version of the brochure	12
Figure 7 Print screen of the monitoring table for the dissemination of the printed version of the brochure	12

Tables

Table 1 Timeline for the brochure dissemination activities	14
--	----

1. Executive summary

This document details the Planetary Health Cluster Brochure, its structure and dissemination plan. The cluster was officially launched and presented on 3 July 2024 in Brussels during a joint event with GoGreen Routes and with the participation of the coordinators of the five projects funded under the Horizon Europe topic HORIZON-HLTH-2023-ENVHLTH-02-01 “Planetary health: understanding the links between environmental degradation and health impacts.” The five projects that form the Planetary Health Cluster are [SPRINGS](#), [PLANET4HEALTH](#), [TULIP](#), [MOSAIC](#), and [GoGreen Next](#).

The produced brochure may be subject to revisions, following changes of the Planetary Health Cluster chair and evaluation of the activities. It will follow the modalities that were agreed upon within the cluster and with the European Commission (EC).

The following sections provide an overview of the Planetary Health Cluster Brochure, its dissemination strategy and actions through a targeted plan, to reach the target audiences and the relevant stakeholder communities. The primary goal is to raise awareness about Planetary health and promote the dissemination of the Planetary Health Cluster’s initiatives.

2. Introduction

2.1. Purpose and scope

The Planetary Health Cluster brochure is designed to provide clear and visually engaging information about the Cluster and its objectives. A poster has been designed and integrated within the brochure and can be utilized independently as well.

The brochure design and content were prepared by the PLANET4HEALTH project, in collaboration with Working Group 3 Communication and Dissemination.

The brochure serves as an informative resource aimed at raising awareness about the Planetary Health Cluster, encouraging readers to explore further by visiting the cluster’s website, thereby increasing its reach and attracting more visitors. Its purpose is to deliver key details in a well-structured and easy-to-understand format, available for both digital and print distribution.

2.2. Audience

This document has been developed for the entire Planetary Health Cluster community, with a particular emphasis on the members of Working Group 3, who are responsible for

disseminating and communicating project-related tasks. Communication experts from each project will play a key role in advancing the Cluster's communication efforts. Additionally, this document has been created as an informative resource for the European Commission project officers overseeing the Cluster's development and progress.

3. The brochure

3.1. Language and tone

The Planetary Health Cluster brochure has been designed to communicate clear, engaging information in alignment with the Cluster's website. Its content, available in English, is written in straightforward language to ensure that key messages are easily understood by all stakeholders. The brochure includes concise explanations, simplifying complex terms and concepts, and visually highlights the most important information for quick reference.

3.2. Structure

An innovative design has been implemented for the Planetary Cluster Brochure, featuring a poster inside that can be used separately. The brochure is optimised for an A3-sized page and folded into four sections, while the poster is also in A3 format. The brochure folding system is shown below:

Figure 1 Folding system of the Planetary Health Brochure

The brochure cover displays the cluster logo, the logos of the 5 Horizon Europe projects, funding disclaimer, and the link to [Planetary Health Cluster website](#). To make visiting the website easier, we've included a QR code both in the brochure and on the poster.

The main section of the brochure outlines the core objectives, mission, goals, and includes a list and description of each Working Group, along with the leading projects. The idea was to keep the brochure focused on essential information, avoiding overwhelming details such as individual project links or emails, and instead directing readers to the cluster website for more comprehensive information.

The poster incorporated into the brochure presents essential information about the cluster, along with the logos of all projects and a funding disclaimer. To maintain consistency in encouraging the audience to visit the website for more information, a QR code linking to the cluster website is also included on the poster.

Figure 2 Front and back covers of the brochure

Figure 3 Interior of the brochure

Figure 4 Planetary Health Cluster poster, part of the brochure

Figure 5 Two-side view, Planetary Health Cluster brochure and poster

3.3. Design

The design of the cluster brochure aligns with the Planetary Health Cluster’s visual identity and branding guidelines, ensuring consistency across all materials. By following these guidelines, the brochure reinforces the cluster’s established visual presence through cohesive design elements, colours, and style.

The colour palette mirrors that of the cluster’s logo and website, helping to maintain a unified identity. These colours symbolise the connection among all projects, while the brochure features consistent design elements and symbols, including icons that align with the overall identity. Additionally, pictures from the website have been included to enhance recognisability, allowing readers to easily identify the cluster through its distinct design.

Developed by the F6S design team for the PLANET4HEALTH project, the brochure emphasises a modern, vibrant, and visually striking design. Elements such as circular motifs evoke movement, community, and action, ensuring the content is both engaging and impactful, while also reflecting the concept of Planetary health.

4. Dissemination plan

4.1. Target audience

The target audience of the brochure includes the seven main stakeholder groups identified in the Cluster Communication and Dissemination plan, which closely aligns with the audience of the Planetary Health Cluster website (<https://planetaryhealthcluster.eu/>).

The key stakeholder groups identified in the Cluster Communication and Dissemination plan, are:

1. Researchers and academia
2. Climate, environment professionals
3. Policy makers
4. Policy experts
5. Funding agencies
6. Civil society
7. Healthcare sector

The goal for all target groups is consistent: to raise interest and motivate them to explore the cluster's website for further details. This brochure is designed to be concise, providing essential information that encourages audiences to visit the website for more insights.

4.2. Distribution channels

The distribution channels have been strategically chosen to align with the target audience and the primary goals of the brochure, which are to inform, promote, and educate about the critical topic focused on Planetary health and understanding the links between environmental degradation and health. By combining both digital and print channels, we aim to maximize the brochure's reach and impact. The brochure will be made available for both digital and physical distribution and will be added to the cluster website upon submission of this deliverable.

The chosen distribution channels include:

Printed brochure distribution channels:

- **In-person events:** Distributing and displaying brochures at conferences, conventions, seminars, workshops, and other events attended by the target audience, including researchers and academia, climate, environment professionals, policy makers, policy experts, funding agencies, civil society, and the healthcare sector.

Each project coordinator will be invited to suggest relevant international and European events to the Planetary Health Cluster coordinating team, where the cluster could be represented and promoted. The first upcoming event identified in the Common Communication and Dissemination plan is the Planetary Health Alliance Annual Meeting, scheduled for October 2025 at Erasmus University in Rotterdam. The second event is the Planetary Health Cluster Annual Meeting, scheduled for

June 2025, where we will meet the Climate Health Cluster and have the opportunity to engage with policymakers and other key stakeholders.

- **Strategic locations:** Placing brochures in strategic locations frequented by the target audience, such as project partners offices, or other places related with the Planetary health topics. For example, for the PLANET4HEALTH project, the brochure could be displayed at the Institute for Medical Research, CICERO - Centre for International Climate Research, or any other relevant partner institution. Additionally, the projects are encouraged to display the interior poster in locations like relevant research centres, among others.
- **Scientific conferences:** Brochures can be displayed at scientific conferences, exhibitions or events focused on Planetary health and its impacts. Each project partner can bring the brochures to these events, leave them at their booths, and share them with other project partners and attendees. Additionally, the poster can be displayed at conference booths or similar venues to raise awareness about Planetary health and the cluster's work.

Digital brochure distribution channels:

- **Website:** The digital brochure will be uploaded to the Planetary Health Cluster's website as well as to the websites of all the projects within the Cluster: [Tulip](#), [Go Green Next](#), [MOSAIC](#), [Planet4Health](#), [SPINGS](#), making it easily accessible for download or viewing.
- **Email marketing:** The brochure can be shared through email marketing campaigns, either as an attachment or a link, to reach stakeholders. Each project from the Cluster is encouraged to include the brochure in their own email campaigns to further promote it.
- **Social media:** The digital brochure will be shared on the [Planetary Health LinkedIn page](#) with engaging posts and links to increase visibility. Promotion will primarily take place through the Planetary Health Cluster LinkedIn page, while each project within the cluster can also contribute by sharing posts or running campaigns on their respective LinkedIn profiles.
- **Online communities and forums:** Sharing the digital brochure on relevant online communities, forums, or discussion boards where the target audience participates.
- **Newsletters:** The digital brochure will be included in newsletters distributed to subscribers of the Planetary Health Cluster newsletter, as well as in the newsletters of individual projects within the cluster, if the projects have newsletter campaigns as part of their Communication and Dissemination strategy.

4.3. Monitoring

The Common Communication and Dissemination Plan highlights that the key performance indicator (KPI) for the cluster brochure is the number of views and downloads on both the

cluster website and project websites. To track this, the PLANET4HEALTH team has developed a simple [document](#).

CLUSTER PROJECTS WEBSITES				PLANETARY HEALTH CLUSTER WEBSITE		
Date	Name of the project	No of views on the project website	No of brochure downloads on project website	Date	No of views	No of brochure downloads
	PLANET4HEALTH					
	TULIP					
	MOSAIC					
	SPRINGS					
	GOGREEN NEXT					

Figure 6 Print screen of the monitoring table for the dissemination of the digital version of the brochure

Additionally, a separate tracking sheet has been created to monitor the distribution of the printed version of the brochure.

Date	Name of the project	No of printed brochures disseminated	Target audience	Event where the brochure was disseminated	City, Country
	PLANET4HEALTH				
	TULIP				
	MOSAIC				
	SPRINGS				
	GOGREEN NEXT				

Figure 7 Print screen of the monitoring table for the dissemination of the printed version of the brochure

These files are available in the cluster repository and are intended for use by all members of Working Group 3, who are responsible for the dissemination and communication of

project-related tasks. Team members are advised to update the document with their results every six months or whenever a project distributes the brochure.

4.4. Timeline

The Cluster will start the dissemination of the brochure in February 2025, and will continue the dissemination until the end of the Cluster activity. The table presents a tentative timeline for the activities related to the dissemination of the cluster brochure.

Table 1 Timeline for the brochure dissemination activities

Name of the task	2025		2026		2027		2028
	Feb-Jun	Jul-Dec	Jan-Jun	Jul-Dec	Jan-Jun	Jul-Dec	Jan-Jun
Update the project website with the brochure	x						
Dissemination of the printed version at events	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Dissemination of social media campaigns	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Dissemination on cluster newsletters	x					x	x
Update the monitoring file	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

Table 1 Timeline for the brochure dissemination activities

5. Conclusion

The development of the cluster brochure marks a significant step in advancing the Planetary Health Cluster's communication efforts. Through the collaborative work of the Working Group 3 team, a valuable resource has been created that emphasises the cluster's focus on Planetary health as a solutions-oriented, multi-dimensional approach. By presenting this complex topic through the cluster's mission and an overview of its working groups in a clear,

concise, and accessible way, the brochure aims to engage diverse audiences and enhance their understanding of the cluster's objectives, while encouraging them to visit the cluster website for further information.

Ongoing updates will be made to the brochure as needed, ensuring that any necessary content changes are incorporated to keep it relevant and aligned with the Cluster's objectives.

6. Annex 1: Planetary Health Cluster brochure

PLANETARY
Health Cluster

**A solutions oriented,
multi-dimensional
health approach**

planetaryhealthcluster.eu
Planetary Health Cluster

**Engage
with us!**

The five Horizon Europe projects: GoGreen Next, MOSAIC, PLANET4HEALTH, SPRINGS, and TULIP form the Planetary Health Cluster.

Funded by
the European Union

The projects that form the Planetary Health Cluster have received funding from the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No.101027764 (SPRINGS), No.101136652 (PLANET4HEALTH), No.101137209 (GoGreen Next), No. 101137398 (MOSAIC), No. 101136659 (TULIP).

The Planetary Health Cluster is formed by five projects funded under the call HORIZON-HLT-2023-ENVHLTH-02-01 "Planetary health: understanding the links between environmental degradation and health."

The Planetary Health Cluster, launched in 2024, comprises five projects:

GoGreen Next (gogreennext.eu), SPRINGS (springsproject.eu), TULIP (tulip-project.eu), MOSAIC (mosaic-europe.eu) and PLANET4HEALTH (planet4health.eu).

Planetary health studies how environmental degradation impacts human health and all life on earth, and works to promote evidence-based policies that protect and restore natural systems for a sustainable future.

Through joint deliverables, co-hosted events, and a shared strategy, these projects will work collectively to promote evidence-based policies that support improved global planetary health.

Promote and disseminate our research on the effects of environmental degradation and its implications for planetary health.

Raise awareness and understanding of the impact of environmental degradation on human health and of the costs and benefits of action and inaction.

Increase dissemination through the cluster's network and communication channels.

Contribute to evidence-based decision-making and more effective EU and global policies.

Build capacity for planetary health research and policy development.

Working Group 1: Science translation for policy and practice

Our goal is to bridge the gap between scientific research and actionable solutions for planetary health. We are undertaking interdisciplinary research that addresses policymakers' needs, promoting best practices, and fostering collaboration among scientists, policymakers, and practitioners. We endeavor to make complex environmental and health data more accessible, identify barriers to implementing science-based solutions, and propose strategies to overcome them through knowledge co-creation that effectively addresses policy, societal, and ecological needs.

Working Group 2: Data methodologies

We are working together to develop common approaches to data and metadata production, management, processing, integrity, quality and dissemination. Taking a common approach aims to enhance data sharing between the cluster projects and beyond, enable collaboration, and harmonize our efforts.

Working Group 3: Communication and Dissemination

The cluster is undertaking a range of coordinated action to promote and disseminate our research, enhance public understanding of planetary health, and raise awareness about the health impacts of environmental degradation.

PLANETARY
Health Cluster

**A solutions oriented,
multi-dimensional
health approach**

The Planetary Health Cluster is formed by five projects funded under the call HORIZON-HLTH-2023-ENVHLTH-02-01 "Planetary health: understanding the links between environmental degradation and health."

**Engage
with us!**

planetaryhealthcluster.eu
Planetary Health Cluster

The five Horizon Europe projects: GoGreen Next, MOSAIC, PLANET4HEALTH, SPRINGS, and TULIP form the Planetary Health Cluster.

Funded by
the European Union

The projects that form the Planetary Health Cluster have received funding from the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement: No.101057764 (SPRINGS), No.101136652 (PLANET4HEALTH), No.101137209 (GoGreen Next), No. 101137398 (MOSAIC), No. 101136659 (TULIP).

PLANETARY Health Cluster

FORMED BY

MOSAIC

SPRINGS

TULIP
planting health